

Kinetics and Mechanism of the Reaction between *cis*- $[\text{Coen}_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]^{3+}$ Ion and Salicylic Acid in 30% Ethanol-Water Mixture

CHHAYA CHAUDHURY* and Late S. K. SIDDHANTA

Department of Chemistry, Durgapur Women's College, Durgapur-713 209

Manuscript received 26 October 1987, revised 29 November 1989, accepted 30 March 1990

Kinetics of substitution of aquo-ligands from *cis*- $[\text{Coen}_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]^{3+}$ by salicylic acid in water-ethanol medium has been studied spectrophotometrically. The overall reaction was found to take place through an ion-pair mechanism, followed by the outersphere-innersphere interchange reaction. The reaction rate was found to be pH-dependent in the pH range 4.0–4.75. The relation between pseudo-first order rate constant k_{obs} and $[\text{OH}^-]$ was found to be

$$k_{\text{obs}} = k_1 + k[\text{OH}^-]$$

where k_1 and k are constants. It was therefore suggested that the ion pair IP is converted to the innersphere complex through an interchange reaction in two parallel paths: one uncatalysed I_a or I_d path with rate constant k_1 and the other (OH^-) -catalysed I_a or I_d path (i.e. SNCB path) with catalytic rate constant k .

The studies by various authors¹ on the kinetics of substitution of aquo-ligands in *cis*- $[\text{Coen}_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]^{3+}$ by oxalate ion, glycinate ion and picolinic acid have established that such anation reaction proceed through I_a mechanism.

Succo and Venturini² studied the rate of reaction of hexaquoaluminium(III) with salicylic acid using stopped-flow technique. In this case, the kinetic behaviour could be interpreted in terms of the dissociative mechanism proposed by Eigen³ which involves the formation of an ion-pair in a fast equilibrium step followed by the slow formation of a pentacoordinated intermediate in the inner-coordination sphere; the penta-coordinated intermediate then captures the ligand from the outersphere in a fast step.

The kinetics of the interaction of hexaquochromium(III) with salicylic acid was studied by Tyagi and Khan⁴ and the authors concluded that the mechanism of this reaction was I_a . Again, the kinetics of the anation of *cis*-aquoamminebis(ethylenediamine)cobalt(III) by salicylate and the kinetics of anation of aquopentaamminecobalt(III) by salicylate were studied by Dash and Mohanti⁵ and the mechanism suggested in each of the two cases was I_d . Ghosh *et al.*⁶ studied the kinetics of substitution of diaquotetraamminecobalt(III) by salicylate.

The above studies prompted us to investigate the kinetics of substitution of aquo-ligands in *cis*- $[\text{Coen}_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]^{3+}$ by salicylic acid in water-ethanol mixture.

Experimental

Preparation of compounds: *cis*- $[\text{Coen}_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]^{3+}$ (NO_3)₃ was prepared⁷ and characterised (Found: Co, 14.9; N, 24.46. Calcd.: Co, 14.69; N, 24.44%); λ_{max} 360 (log $\epsilon=1.805$) and 495 nm (1.90). These compared favourably with literature data⁸.

Ammonium hydrosalicylate was prepared from salicylic acid, washed with alcohol and then with ether (Found: N, 9.05. $\text{C}_6\text{H}_4(\text{OH})\text{COONH}_4$ calcd. for: N, 9.03%).

cis-Dihydrosalicylatobis(ethylenediamine)cobalt(III) nitrate, i.e. *cis*- $[\text{Coen}_2(\text{ortho-C}_6\text{H}_4(\text{OH})\text{COO})_2]^{2+}$ (NO_3)₂: Bright red crystals of *cis*- $[\text{Coen}_2(\text{ortho-C}_6\text{H}_4(\text{OH})\text{COO})_2]^{2+}$ (NO_3)₂ were separated by mixing a solution of *cis*- $[\text{Coen}_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]^{3+}$ (NO_3)₃ and ammonium hydrosalicylate at room temperature in 1:2 molar ratio in 30% (v/v) ethanol-water mixture at pH 4.0; the crystals were air-dried and analysed (Found: Co, 11.50; N, 13.8. *cis*- $[\text{Coen}_2(\text{C}_6\text{H}_4(\text{OH})\text{COO})_2]^{2+}$ (NO_3)₂ calcd. for: Co, 11.44; N, 13.58%); λ_{max} 340 ($\epsilon=270.0$) and 500 nm (162.0), λ_{min} 420 nm ($\epsilon=25.0$).

trans- $[\text{Coen}_2(\text{ortho-C}_6\text{H}_4(\text{OH})\text{COO})_2]^{2+}$ (NO_3)₂: Bright fluorescent pinkish red crystals of *trans*- $[\text{Coen}_2(\text{ortho-C}_6\text{H}_4(\text{OH})\text{COO})_2]^{2+}$ (NO_3)₂ were separated by refluxing on a hot water-bath a solution of *cis*- $[\text{Coen}_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]^{3+}$ and ammonium hydrosalicylate in 1:2 molar ratio in 30% (v/v) ethanol-water at pH 4.0; the crystals were air-dried and analysed (Found: Co, 11.55; N, 13.76. *trans*- $[\text{Coen}_2(\text{C}_6\text{H}_4(\text{OH})\text{COO})_2]^{2+}$ (NO_3)₂ calcd. for: Co, 11.44; N, 13.58%). It was characterised to be

the *trans*-complex, $\lambda_{\max}$ 350 ($\epsilon=220.0$), 450 (28 2) and 550 nm (72 8), $\lambda_{\min}$ 420 nm ($\epsilon=24.4$)

The absorption spectra of 0.005 M *cis* [Coen₂-(H₂O)₂]³⁺ along with 0.005 M *cis*- and *trans*-bis-hydrosalicylate product [Coen₂(ortho-C₆H₄(OH)-COO)₂]⁺ in 30% (v/v) ethanol-water medium have been shown in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. Absorption spectra of 0.005 M solution of (I□) *cis*-[Coen₂(H₂O)₂](NO₃)₃, (II○) *cis* [Coen₂(HL)₂](NO₃) in and (IIIΔ) *trans*-[Coen₂(HL)₂](NO₃) in 30% ethanol; cell length = 2 cm.

pK values of salicylic acid: The first acid dissociation constant k_1 of salicylic acid was determined in 30% (v/v) ethanol-water mixture at ionic strength 0.18 M and at 35° by Irving-Rossotti method⁹. The pK_1 value obtained was 3.92.

Studies in composition and kinetics: The composition of the complex formed between *cis*-[Coen₂(H₂O)₂]³⁺ and hydrosalicylate ion in solution at pH 4.0 was determined by Job's method of continuous variations. It was found that one mole of the cobalt(III) complex reacts with two moles of hydrosalicylate ion. This shows that under our reaction conditions, only the *cis*-dihydrosalicylate product is formed. We noted that the solution mixture of *cis*-[Coen₂(H₂O)₂]³⁺ and ammonium hydrosalicylate has to be refluxed on hot water-bath to obtain the *trans*-product, and hence it may be presumed that the *cis*-form of the product is not converted to the *trans*-form at 35°, at which the reaction were studied.

Temperature equilibrated solutions of ammonium hydrosalicylate and the *cis*-diaquo complex (A) of desired concentrations, were mixed and the course of the reaction was followed by measuring absorbance (Hilger UVISPEK spectrophotometer) at 500 nm, where a substantial difference existed in the spectra of the *cis*-diaquo complex and the *cis*-dihydrosalicylate product (Fig. 1). The investigation was made (i) at 35° in a 30% ethanol water medium at a constant pH 4.0 and a constant ionic strength 0.18 M using constant concentration 0.005 M of the diaquo complex (A) but varying

ammonium hydrosalicylate concentrations as 0.01, 0.015, 0.025, 0.05, 0.10 and 0.15 M and also (ii) at 35° in the same solvent using constant concentration of [A]=0.005 M and [Ammonium hydrosalicylate]=0.05 M but varying pH over the range 4.0–4.75 keeping the ionic strength constant (0.18 M). The pseudo-first order rate constants (k_{obs}) were calculated from the slope of the plots $\log(D_\alpha - D_0)/(D_\alpha - D_t)$ against time t , where D_0 and D_t stand for the optical densities of the reaction mixture at time zero and t respectively; D_α was taken to be equal to the measured optical density of the end-product dihydrosalicylate complex of concentration equal to that of the parent diaquo complex. The pseudo-first order plots were found to be linear in every case from start to finish of the reaction (see Figs. 2 and 5). In Fig. 2, $\log(D_\alpha - D_0)/(D_\alpha - D_t)$ values have been plotted against t at various (NH₄)HL concentrations, and in Fig. 5 at various pH values.

Fig. 2. Effect of varying [HL⁻] on the reaction rate: (IΔ) [(NH₄)HL]=0.05; 0.10; 0.15 M, (II○) [(NH₄)HL]=0.025 M, (III□) [(NH₄)HL]=0.015 M and (IV◇) [(NH₄)HL]=0.01 M; [A]=0.005 M, temp = 35°, pH = 4.00, $\mu=0.18$ M

Fig. 3. Variation of k_{obs} with [HL⁻]; [A]=0.005 M, pH=4.00, $\mu=0.18$ M, temp.=35°.

Fig. 4. Plots of $1/k_{obs}$ vs $1/[HL^-]$.

Fig. 5. Effect of pH on reaction rate at pH: (I□) 4.75, (II△) 4.50, (III○) 4.35 and (IV⊙) 4.00; $[A] = 0.005 M$, $[(NH_4)HL] = 0.05 M$, $\mu = 0.18 M$, temp. = 35° .

The pH was varied by adding nitric acid to the medium, and ionic strength was adjusted by adding sodium nitrate (AR) as required.

Results and Discussion

The complex reaction that takes place between $cis-[Coen_2(H_2O)_2]^{3+}$ and salicylic acid in water-ethanol mixture at pH 4.0 can be depicted as

The following abbreviations were used: ethylenediamine = en; ortho- $C_6H_4(OH)COOH = H_2L$; ortho- $C_6H_4(OH)COO^- = HL^-$; ortho- $C_6H_4(O^-)(COO^-) = L^{2-}$; $cis-[Coen_2(H_2O)_2]^{3+} = A$; $cis-[Coen_2(H_2O)HL]^{2+} = B$; $cis-[Coen_2(HL)_2]^+ = C$.

Presumably the complete reaction (1) occurs in two consecutive steps, each step involving the replacement of one H_2O by one HL^- ,

We could not however isolate the monoquo-mono-hydro-salicylato complex (B) in spite of repeated attempts. We found that the reaction between (A) and ammonium hydro-salicylate, even when taken in the molar proportion 1 : 1, always yielded the *cis*-disubstituted product (C). The only explanation for this is perhaps that reaction (1a) is slow and (1b) is very fast, so that the complex (B) reacted immediately after its formation with hydro-salicylate ion to form the end-product (C) in a very fast step; therefore (B) could not be isolated. All the kinetic studies described here therefore refer only to the first step (1a) of reaction (1). At the pH range 4.0 – 4.75, salicylic acid dissociates mainly as

Since the pK_2 is very high (≈ 11.0), practically no L^{2-} ion is formed in this range of pH. So, we did not find any evidence for the formation of the complex $[Coen_2L]^+$ by replacement of two water molecules in the parent complex by a single chelated salicylate ligand at pH 4.0. The ir band for free salicylic acid due to ν_{C-O} (carboxylic) at 1665 cm^{-1} shifted to 1600 cm^{-1} in the *cis*-di-hydro-salicylatobis(ethylenediamine)cobalt(III) complex (C), indicating the presence of $COO-M$ bond in the coordination zone of (C).

Effect of varying $[HL^-]$ on rate constant: Since HL^- is the reacting species, $[HL^-]$ at various ammonium hydro-salicylate concentrations as calculated from the Henderson's equation,

$$pH = pK_1 + \log \frac{[HL^-]}{[H_2L]} \quad (3)$$

have been shown in Table 1, including k_{obs} and $1/k_{obs}$ values corresponding to different $[HL^-]$. The values of k_{obs} at each pH have been given in Table 2. The values of $[HL^-]$, rather than those of $[NH_4HL]$, were used in Tables 1 and 2 as HL^- is the reactive entity.

TABLE 1 - VARIATION OF RATE CONSTANT WITH $[HL^-]$ AND VARIATION OF $1/k_{obs}$ WITH $1/[HL^-]$ (FIGS. 3 AND 4)

$[A]=0.005 M$, $pH=4.0$, $\mu=0.18 M$, $Temp.=35^\circ$

$[(NH_4)HL]$ M	$[HL^-]$	k_{obs} $\times 10^5 s^{-1}$	$1/[HL^-]$ $\times 10^{-2}$	$1/k_{obs}$ $\times 10^{-5}$
0.010	0.0055	1.26	1.83	0.79
0.015	0.0082	1.56	1.22	0.64
0.025	0.0136	1.93	0.73	0.52
0.050	0.027	2.19	0.37	0.46
0.100	0.055	2.19	-	-
0.150	0.082	2.19	-	-

The value of k_1 obtained from the constant value of k_{obs} at high $[(NH_4)HL]$ using Fig. 3 is $2.2 \times 10^{-5} s^{-1}$. The values for k_1 and K_1 obtained from the slope and intercept of the plot in Fig. 4 are $2.6 \times 10^{-5} s^{-1}$ and $1.8 \times 10^3 dm^3 mol^{-1}$ respectively

 TABLE 2 - VARIATIONS OF THE RATE CONSTANT (k_{obs}) WITH $1/[H^+]$ AND $\log(k_{obs} - k_1)$ WITH pH (FIGS. 6 AND 7)

$[A]=0.005 M$, $[(NH_4)HL]=0.05 M$, $\mu=0.18 M$, $Temp.=35^\circ$

pH	$[H^+]$ $\times 10^2 M$	$[HL^-]$ M	k_{obs} $\times 10^5 s^{-1}$	$1/[H^+]$ $\times 10^{-3} M^{-1}$	$\log(k_{obs} - k_1)$
4.00	10.00	0.027	2.19	10.00	-5.32
4.35	4.47	0.036	2.81	22.39	-4.96
4.50	3.16	0.040	3.23	31.62	-4.82
4.75	1.78	0.044	4.61	56.23	-4.54

Intercept of the plot of k_{obs} vs $1/[H^+]$ on the ordinate = $k_1 = 1.70 \times 10^{-5} s^{-1}$ (Fig. 6)

The slope of the straight line plot $\log(k_{obs} - k_1)$ vs pH is $+1.0$ (Fig. 7)

The results of the variation of rate constant (k_{obs}) with $[HL^-]$ (Table 1) show that when $[HL^-]$ is low, the rate continuously increases with increasing $[HL^-]$, and at high $[HL^-]$, a limiting rate is reached; this happens due to completion of ion-pair (IP) formation. Through our kinetic studies, we could establish that the overall reaction (1) takes place through an ion-pair mechanism followed by slow innersphere-outersphere interchange and rapid capture of the second hydrosalicylate ion by removal of water as shown in Scheme 1.

Scheme 1

The rate law for Scheme 1, would be

$$Rate = \frac{d[C]}{dt} = \frac{k_1 K_1 [A_{un}] [HL^-]}{1 + K_1 [HL^-]} \quad (4)$$

where, K_1 is ion-pair equilibrium constant, k_1 the outersphere-innersphere interchange constant and $[A_{un}]$ the total unreacted [substrate] = $[A] + [IP]$, at time t

$$But \text{ rate} = k_{obs} [A_{un}] \quad (5)$$

Therefore,

$$k_{obs} = \frac{k_1 K_1 [HL^-]}{1 + K_1 [HL^-]} \quad (6)$$

It follows from equation (6) that the plot of k_{obs} vs $[HL^-]$ is a straight line with positive slope to begin with, but the plot takes a curvature with gradually diminishing slope as $[HL^-]$ increases and finally when $[HL^-]$ is high, we get $k_{obs} = k_1$, that is, the plot becomes a straight line again parallel to the abscissa. At this stage, we may presume that ion-pair formation is complete and we can therefore find out the value of k_1 from the value of k_{obs} at this stage. The value of k_{obs} against $[HL^-]$ has been shown in Table 1 and the plot k_{obs} vs $[HL^-]$ in Fig. 3. k_{obs} vs $[HL^-]$ plot (Fig. 3) is linear at low $[HL^-]$, becomes curved with diminishing slope at higher $[HL^-]$ and is a straight line with zero slope when $[HL^-]$ becomes very high. This plot therefore establishes that Scheme 1 is operative in this case. The k_1 value obtained from the value of k_{obs} where the plot is linear and parallel to the abscissa in Fig. 3 is $2.2 \times 10^{-5} s^{-1}$.

Equation (6) also indicates that the plot of $1/k_{obs}$ vs $1/[HL^-]$ should be a straight line with slope $1/k_1 K_1$ and intercept $1/k_1$. Fig. 4 shows that the $1/k_{obs}$ vs $1/[HL^-]$ plot is linear; using the values of the slope and the intercept of this straight line, k_1 and K_1 values have been found to be $2.6 \times 10^{-5} s^{-1}$ and $1.8 \times 10^3 dm^3 mol^{-1}$ respectively. The agreement between the values $k_1 = 2.2 \times 10^{-5} s^{-1}$ as obtained using Fig. 3, and $k_1 = 2.6 \times 10^{-5} s^{-1}$ as obtained using Fig. 4, may be said to be satisfactory considering the approximate nature of the method. This has been found to be so indicating the applicability of equation (6)

The value found for the ion-pair equilibrium constant $K_1 = 1.8 \times 10^3$ at 35° in 30% (v/v) ethanol-water solvent of the tri-univalent ion-pair $[A^{3+}]$. HL^- is rather high compared to other tripositive cobalt complex - uninegative anion pairs in aqueous medium at 25° . This high value may be due to (i) lower dielectric constant of the medium 30% (v/v) ethanol-water mixture as compared to pure water, and (ii) existence of hydrogen bond between OH hydrogen atom of the hydrosalicylate ion in the outersphere and oxygen atom of one coordinated H_2O , or between the H atom of NH_2 in one of the coordinated en and O atom of the OH^- group of hydrosalicylate in the outersphere. However, the

bond dipole¹¹ value of OH is 1.6 d and that of N-H is 1.3 d, suggesting that hydrogen bonding through OH hydrogen atom is stronger than that of through NH hydrogen atom. Therefore we may prefer the first possibility that the hydrogen bonding in the ion-pair is established through the OH hydrogen atom of the entering ligand connecting it with H₂O oxygen atom in the complex.

Effect of varying pH on rate constant: In the next step, we tried to study and interpret the variation of the rate of the reaction with the change of pH of the medium (at fixed [A] = 0.005 M, [(NH₄)HL] = 0.05 M and ionic strength = 0.18 M; temp. = 35°). We have chosen [(NH₄)HL] = 0.05 M, since at this concentration of [(NH₄)HL], *k*_{obs} does not increase further with the increase of [(NH₄)HL] and the ion-pair formation may be considered as complete. It is observed from Table 2 that the rate constants increase with the increase of pH. We therefore presumed that the ion-pair (IP) of Scheme 1, instead of being converted into the mono-aquomonohydrosalicylato complex (B) directly by either I_a or I_d path follows an (OH⁻) ion-catalysed S_NCB mechanism (Scheme 2) by equations (7)–(10).

In reaction (7), the OH hydrogen atom of the hydrosalicylato ion being δ positive, attracts the electron cloud of the O-atom in the H₂O molecule hydrogen-bonded to it and facilitates the release of a proton from this H₂O molecule,

The slow step (8) may follow either I_a and I_d mechanism,

Scheme 2

OH⁻ ion is regenerated in equation (9) and thus Scheme 2 represents an OH⁻ catalysed reaction. In equation (10) the electron density on Co^{III} ion in (B) is considerably increased, thus labilising the remaining coordinated water molecule in (B) which is then easily substituted by another HL⁻ ion resulting the *cis*-dihydrosalicylato complex (C).

Equilibrium (7) of Scheme 2 yields,

$$[(\text{CB})] = K[\text{IP}][\text{OH}^-] \quad (11)$$

The steps (7), (9) and (10) are all fast, the only slow step of the total reaction is step (8). It therefore follows that the rate of formation of the final product C = rate of reaction (8)

$$= k_{\text{OB}}[(\text{CB})] \quad (12)$$

Combining equation (11) with (12) we have,

$$\begin{aligned} \text{rate} &= k_{\text{OB}} K[\text{IP}][\text{OH}^-] \\ &= \frac{k_{\text{OB}} K K_w [\text{I}^2]}{[\text{H}^+]} \quad (13) \end{aligned}$$

where *K_w* is the ionisation constant of water.

Thus $k_{\text{obs}} = \frac{k_{\text{OB}} K K_w}{[\text{H}^+]}$ (14)

Equation (14) predicts that *k*_{obs} vs 1/[H⁺] plot should be a straight line passing through the origin.

The plot of *k*_{obs} vs 1/[H⁺] has been shown in Fig. 6. It will be seen that this plot is a straight

Fig. 6. Plot of *k*_{obs} vs 1/[H⁺]; [A] = 0.005 M, [(NH₄)HL] = 0.05 M, μ = 0.18 M, temp. = 35°, pH = 4.00.

line, but it does not pass through the origin; instead it cuts the ordinate at *k*_{obs} = 1.7 × 10⁻⁵ s⁻¹. Therefore *k*_{obs} can be represented by the equation (15),

$$k_{\text{obs}} = k_1 + \frac{k_{\text{CB}} K K_w}{[\text{H}^+]} \quad (15)$$

Scheme 3

in which k_1 is the intercept and constant $k_{\text{CB}} KK_w$ the slope of the plot k_{obs} vs $1/[\text{H}^+]$.

$$\text{Thus, rate} = k_1[\text{IP}] + \frac{k_{\text{CB}} KK_w [\text{IP}]}{[\text{H}^+]} \quad (16)$$

From equation (16) it is obvious that in the case of the present ion-pair, the outersphere-innersphere interchange reaction takes place in two parallel paths, namely, (i) an uncatalysed I_d or I_a path with rate constant k_1 and (ii) an $\text{S}_\text{N}\text{CB}$ path with rate constant k_{CB} according to Scheme 3.

Fig. 7. Plot of $\log(k_{\text{obs}} - k_1)$ vs pH; $[\text{A}] = 0.005 \text{ M}$, $[(\text{NH}_4)\text{HL}] = 0.05 \text{ M}$, $\mu = 0.18 \text{ M}$, $\text{temp.} = 35^\circ$.

That Scheme 3 is actually operative in the reaction under discussion, was further substantiated in the following ways.

Equation (15) can be transformed into

$$\begin{aligned}
 \log(k_{\text{obs}} - k_1) &= \log \frac{k_{\text{CB}} KK_w}{[\text{H}^+]} \\
 &= \log k_{\text{CB}} KK_w + \text{pH} \quad (17)
 \end{aligned}$$

Equation (17) implies that $\log(k_{\text{obs}} - k_1)$, when plotted against pH, will yield a straight line with slope = +1.0 and intercept = $\log k_{\text{CB}} KK_w$. Fig. 7 shows the plot of $\log(k_{\text{obs}} - k_1)$ vs pH (data in Table 2) which is in fact a straight line with slope of +1.0. Scheme 3 is thus finally established.

References

1. P. M. BROWN and G. M. HARRIS, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1968, 7, 1872; S. K. RAY, Ph.D. Thesis, University of Burdwan, 1972; K. DUTTA and G. S. DE, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1982, 21, 477.
2. F. SUCCO and M. VENTURINI, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1975, 14, 1978.
3. M. EIGEN, *Z. Electrochem.*, 1960, 64, 115.
4. S. C. TYAGI and A. A. KHAN, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1979, 41, 1899.
5. A. C. DASH and B. MOHANTY, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1979, 41, 1053; *Indian J. Chem.*, 1979, 17, 296.
6. GHOSH, BHATTACHARYA and BANERJEE, *Trans. Met. Chem.*, 1984, 9, 68.
7. F. P. DWYER, A. M. SARGESON and L. K. REID, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1963, 85, 1219.
8. F. APRILE, V. CAGLIATI and G. ILLUMINATI, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1961, 21, 300.
9. H. IRVING and H. S. ROSSOTTI, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, 2904.
10. F. BASOLO and R. G. PEARSON, "Mechanism of Inorganic Reactions", 2nd ed., Wiley Eastern, New Delhi, 1977, p. 37.
11. P. C. RAKSHIT, "Physical Chemistry", 4th ed., Science Book Agency, Calcutta, 1980, p. 321.